

Flexible Fabrication-Driven Design Approach for Product Development in Fab Labs

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Abstract

Purpose: This paper examines a flexible, fabrication-driven design methodology in Fab Labs, highlighting how digital fabrication tools enable customizable, scalable product development. It explores the benefits, challenges, and implications of this approach in modern manufacturing.

Design/Methodology/Approach: A practice-based methodology is used to analyse modular product systems with adjustable connections for applications such as furniture, stage sets, and automotive tuning. The study integrates theoretical discussions on digital fabrication with practical insights from case studies and prototyping experiments.

Data/Sample: The research evaluates design iterations, fabrication test results, and user feedback from Fab Lab environments to assess flexibility, efficiency, and adaptability.

Findings: A fabrication-driven approach enhances adaptability, reduces material waste, and optimises customization. Modular and parametric design strategies improve digital fabrication efficiency, making them ideal for small-scale manufacturing and prototyping. This approach proves effective across multiple domains.

Research Limitations/Implications: Scalability may be limited by specific digital fabrication tools. Future research could explore large-scale applications and long-term product durability.

Practical Implications: Integrating fabrication-driven principles into Fab Lab workflows improves prototyping, efficiency, and innovation, supporting cost-effective and sustainable product development.

Originality/Value: This study offers insights into digital fabrication and flexible design, benefiting Fab Lab practitioners, industrial designers, and engineers optimising customisation and production efficiency.

Keywords

Design, fabrication, prototyping, fab lab

1 Introduction

In recent years, digital fabrication technologies have revolutionised the way products are designed and manufactured. Fab Labs provide an ideal environment for experimentation and innovation, using tools such as CNC machines, 3D printers, and laser cutters. This paper explores the advantages, potential obstacles, and wider impact of a flexible fabrication-driven design approach within the modern manufacturing and design practices. By examining its practical applications, limitations, and long-term implications, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of its role in the evolving industrial landscape.

The objective of this approach is to create a sustainable model for flexible production, ensuring adaptability to changing product requirements. This includes variations in functional characteristics, aesthetics, production scale, and manufacturing constraints. By integrating parametric design and

modular fabrication principles, this methodology seeks to streamline the transition from concept to final product, enhancing both efficiency and customisation opportunities.

Theoretical Background

The fabrication-driven design methodology builds upon established research in digital fabrication and parametric design. The study of Barrios Hernandez (Hernandez, 2006) has introduced computational frameworks allowing for the efficient generation of parametric design solutions, significantly influencing the adaptability of modular product systems. Similarly, Roland Hudson (Hudson, 2010) discusses the emerging role of parametric designers in integrating design processes within the construction industry, which aligns with our research focus on modular fabrication strategies.

A research in co-creation and digital fabrication of Sehrisha Khan and his team (Khan et al. 2023) suggests that collaboration within makerspaces improves innovation and efficiency. This perspective supports our discussion on the impact of flexible fabrication within Fab Labs.

2 Design/Methodology/Approach

To analyse the impact of this methodology, we examine the products resulting from its practical application. These products can be divided into three main categories:

Products constructed from parametrically designed parts and modules.

Products incorporating pre-designed Adjustable Reassemblable Connections (ARCTONIC)

Products featuring polygonal surface geometry (PolygonG)

Each of these categories illustrates a different facet of flexible fabrication, providing an understanding of how digital design methodologies influence material selection, structural efficiency, adaptability, and aesthetics.

2.1 Products Constructed from Parametrically Designed Parts and Modules.

This category focuses on designs based on steel sheet details, where each component is parametrically designed and manufactured through laser cutting. The ability to parametrically define components enables rapid modifications, ensuring design flexibility and consistency across multiple iterations. This approach is particularly useful for applications that demand high precision and scalability, such as automotive, furniture and architectural structures.

Fabrication

The concept has been tested through various projects, including:

- A car frame: This structure was designed with precisely cut steel sheets, ensuring accurate hole alignment for bolted connections;
- A stage car: Used in theatrical performances, requiring lightweight yet rigid structures;
- Mold sets for matrix production: These modules serve as master forms for producing fiberglass parts, requiring high geometric accuracy.

The fabrication process involves the following steps:

- Design: structures are modelled using parametric CAD software;
- Cutting: laser cutting ensures precision and repeatability;
- Assembly and welding: components are assembled and welded to form the final structure;
- Finishing: includes sanding, surface treatment, and painting.

Key features

The utilisation of laser-cut parts offers several advantages:

- High precision: dimensional accuracy is independent of human error;
- Cost efficiency: material waste is reduced and fabrication time is optimised;
- Scalability: it enables both one-off productions and mass manufacturing without additional tooling costs;
- Customisation: modifications can be implemented swiftly due to the parametric nature of the design.

For all the three projects mentioned, the precision of fabrication of the main structure is of particular importance. For both vehicles, the accuracy of the frame connection holes determines the proper functioning of all the units and mechanisms attached to them. In the structure of the matrix model, not only the accuracy of certain dimensions is important, but also the precision of the entire surface, which is intended to be subsequently multiplied in large scale production.

Outcome and Challenges

The implementation of these projects satisfies two primary requirements:

Design feasibility: meeting technical and functional requirements while maintaining cost efficiency;

Flexibility: allowing scalable production and easy design modifications without major reinvestment.

However, challenges include:

- welding limitations for specific materials (e.g., aluminium, stainless steel);
- quality control issues in welded joints;
- post-processing requirements, such as grinding and finishing;
- repair limitations: welded structures are more difficult to modify or repair once deformed;
- constraints on welding in certain environments, such as theatre stages and confined spaces.

These challenges highlight the need for alternative joining techniques, leading to the development of Adjustable Reassemblable Connections (ARCTONIC).

2.2 Products Incorporating Pre-Designed Adjustable Reassemblable Connections (ARCTONIC)

Concept

Adjustable Reassemblable Connections (ARCTONIC) allow structures to be assembled without welding. These connections enhance flexibility, enabling structures to be disassembled, adjusted, and reconfigured with ease. This is particularly beneficial in scenarios requiring modularity and rapid prototyping.

Examples of ARCTONIC are presented below.

2.2.1 Bolt-and-Nut Fastened Connection Concept

A bolt-and-nut fastened connection that joins perpendicular sheet metal components with increased stability. Utilises additional plates to secure nuts in pre-cut slots, eliminating the need for a second wrench.

Figure 1 illustrates the mounting components used to join two flat parts, labelled as (2) and (3), which are positioned perpendicularly to each other. Each nut (4) is placed within a T-slot (2.1) that is specifically designed for it, along with a corresponding plate (1).

The plate (1) features two slots (1.1) that must match the thickness of part (2). During assembly, the plate is first inserted into the T-slot, followed by the nut. The primary role of the plate is to secure the bolt (5) to part (2). The T-slot is designed to hold the nut in place, preventing it from rotating when the bolt is tightened. This eliminates the need for a second wrench when assembling the joint.

However, because the nut slots weaken part (2) structurally, additional reinforcement may be necessary in high-load applications. To compensate for this, extra tabs (2.2) and slots (3.1) can be added for increased strength.

Practical Implementation

The components in these assemblies can be made of various materials. In our practice, plate 1 is typically made of 2mm thick stainless steel sheet. Many of our constructions are produced using only 2mm thick sheet metal, with all parts laser-cut. For heavier structures such as stairs and railings, we use material with thickness up to 6mm. In other applications, materials such as plywood, wood, or polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) are used for the parts containing holes, but the nut slot parts are always made of sheet steel for durability.

Figure 1: Bolt-and-nut fastened connection

2.2.2 Profile to Sheet Connection Concept

This mechanical assembly is used to connect a cylindrical profile (such as a tube) with two flat details (such as beams or plates) at a perpendicular angle. The connection is reinforced using two brackets, a bolt, and a nut. The main components, shown in Figure 2, are:

- cylindrical profile (6): a tube or rod that runs along its longitudinal axis (6.1);
- flat details (3): two plates positioned perpendicularly to each other;
- brackets (1 & 2): additional support elements that hold the assembly together;
- bolt (4) & nut (5): used to tighten the assembly.

Assembly Process

The first bracket (1) has two holes (1.3) that match the cross-section of the cylindrical profile, allowing it to fit securely. The second bracket (2) has hooks (2.2) that engage with elongated holes (3.1) in the flat details, ensuring alignment. The first bracket holds the bolt (4), which passes through a hole (2.3) in the second bracket. The nut (5) is screwed onto the bolt. When the nut is tightened, the brackets move towards each other, pressing the cylindrical profile and flat details firmly together. This creates a secure joint that can be easily assembled and disassembled by loosening or tightening the nut.

Practical Applications

This assembly method is useful for vertical columns and beams in various structures. It works with metal tubes (circular or rectangular) or solid wooden profiles (preferably hard woods like beech or ash). The brackets are made of 2 mm thick sheet steel for durability.

It has been successfully tested in structures such as tables, stools, shelves, theatre stages, ladders, easels, and exterior kiosks.

Outcome and Challenges

Metal profiles perform better since they don't deform over time. Wooden profiles may loosen due to small contact areas, requiring periodic tightening. This system provides a strong, stable, and reusable connection that simplifies assembly and disassembly using just a single nut.

Figure 2: Profile to Sheet Connection

2.2.3 Table Leg with Adjustable Mounting

A table leg with adjustable mounting can be fixed to a table top without requiring holes or modifications to the surface. It allows for attachment to various materials, including wood, glass, and stone.

This table leg assembly consists of three metal parts and is designed to be easily attached to a table top without requiring modifications to the surface.

The components of the table leg assembly are:

- sheet metal parts (2, 3, 4) (Figure 3): these three metal pieces form the structure of the leg;
- bolts and nuts (8): six sets of bolts and nuts hold the three metal parts together;
- rivet nut (7): this is a standard type of nut that is fixed inside hole 4.1 of detail 4.
- bolt (6): this bolt screws into the rivet nut and is used to press sheet detail 5 against the table top (1). This additional sheet detail (5) helps secure the leg to the table.

How the Assembly Works

The three sheet metal parts (2, 3, and 4) are fastened together using six bolts with nuts (8) to form a stable leg structure. A rivet nut (7) is installed in hole 4.1 of detail 4. A bolt (6) is screwed into this rivet nut to push detail 5 firmly against the table top (1). This setup ensures that details 2 and 5 hold the leg securely to the table top.

Key Features of the Design

The leg parts are made of 2 mm thick stainless steel for strength and durability. Laser cutting was used to shape the parts, and the folds were made using a bending machine. No holes, grooves, or other modifications are required on the table top. This means the legs can be attached to any surface without drilling.

The design allows for versatile installation on different table top materials, including glued wood, plywood, glass, granite, and acrylic stone.

Summary

This table leg system is innovative because it allows legs to be attached to a table top without the need of drilling or modifying the surface. It provides a strong, stable connection while allowing flexibility in choosing the table top material.

Figure 3: Table Leg with Adjustable Mounting

2.2.4 Multi-Profile Joint

This assembly joins three or four profiles at non-parallel angles. Optionally, a table top can be mounted symmetrically to them. It enables the creation of complex support structures, such as shelves and furniture frames.

The components of the assembly are:

- three cylindrical profiles (2), (Figure 4): these are evenly spaced at 120-degree angles in three different planes;
- housing (3): this part contains grooves (3.1) that match the shape and position of the profiles, helping hold them in place;
- upper core (4) & lower core (5): these two parts sandwich the profiles to secure them;
- bolt (6) & nut (7): these fasteners are used to tighten the assembly and lock the profiles together;
- additional detail (1) (optional): a separate component that can be attached to the assembly using a hole made in it.

How the Assembly Works

The three cylindrical profiles are arranged symmetrically, each forming a 120-degree angle relative to the others. They do not share a common axis but are evenly spaced apart. The housing (3) has specially shaped grooves (3.1) that hold the profiles in their precise positions. The upper core (4) and lower core (5) are placed on opposite sides of the housing. The bolt (6) passes through the cores and is tightened against the nut (7). This compression force pushes the cores together, which in turn presses the profiles tightly against the housing (3), ensuring a secure and stable connection.

Attaching an Additional Detail

The bolt (6) can also be used to secure an additional detail (1) that has a hole in it, allowing for extra functionality or customisation of the assembly.

Key Features of the Design

- **Stable and Strong Connection:** the assembly firmly holds three cylindrical profiles together without the need of welding or permanent modifications;
- **Adjustability:** by loosening the bolt (6), the profiles can be repositioned or replaced easily;
- **Expandable design:** the assembly allows for the attachment of extra components (e.g. detail 1), making it versatile for different applications.

Practical Applications

This type of three-profile connector is commonly used in:

- structural frames (e.g. modular constructions, display stands, furniture);
- scaffolding systems requiring strong, non-welded joints;
- mechanical and industrial assemblies where cylindrical profiles need to be joined securely.

The three-profile assembly from Figure 4 is practically used in real-world applications, particularly in a three-legged stool-table. The three profiles (legs) serve as the legs of the stool or table. They can be made of wood to create a natural appearance. Alternatively, steel tubes can be used for durability and strength. The body (housing) and the two cores (upper and lower) are 3D-printed from ABS plastic, making the structure lightweight and easy to manufacture. The seat or table top (seat-floor) can be made of various materials such as:

- plywood (for a classic wooden finish);
- PMMA (for a modern, transparent design);
- acrylic stone (for a solid, premium feel).

Other Practical Applications

The same three-profile assembly has also been successfully used in:

- three-legged tables (small, stable tables using the same leg structure);
- light fixtures (where three supports hold a lighting element);
- shelves (using three cylindrical supports for stability);
- clothes hangers (creating freestanding or wall-mounted designs).

Key Benefits of This Design

- **versatile materials:** legs can be made of wood or metal, while the seat/table top can be made of various materials;
- **lightweight yet strong:** the 3D-printed ABS body and cores keep the structure lightweight while maintaining strength;
- **no need for drilling or welding:** the profiles are fixed using a bolt and nut system, making assembly and disassembly easy;

- multi-purpose design: the same assembly can be adapted for furniture, lighting, shelving, and more.

Summary

This assembly efficiently joins three cylindrical profiles in a 120-degree symmetrical arrangement using a housing, two cores, a bolt, and a nut. The profiles are pressed securely into grooves within the housing, and an additional detail can be attached if needed. This design is both rigid and adaptable, allowing for easy assembly and disassembly.

Figure 4: Multi-Profile Joint

2.2.5 Spherical Joint for Cylindrical Profiles

Spherical joint for cylindrical profiles provide variable mobility through adjustable tightening mechanisms. It is used in dynamic structures such as mannequins and adjustable lighting fixtures.

Figure 5 shows a spherical joint that connects a cylindrical detail (1) to an elongated nut (8) using a sphere (3), two housings (2), reinforcing plates (4 and 5), and bolts/nuts. This joint allows controlled movement and can be tightened for rigidity.

The components of the spherical joint are:

- a cylindrical detail (1): the main tube or rod that connects to the joint;
- an elongated nut (8): a long nut that provides a secure connection;
- a sphere (3): the central element that allows rotational movement;

- two symmetrical housings (2): these encase the sphere and help secure the joint;
- reinforcing plates (4 & 5): plates 5 fit into plates 4 using grooves (5.2) and holes (4.1). The holes (4.1) are shaped to prevent the hex nut from rotating, allowing tightening by turning only the bolt;
- bolt (9): is used to tighten the sphere (3) to the elongated nut (8);
- nut & bolt (6): they pass through holes (5.1) to press the housings (2) against the sphere (3) and profile (1), locking them together.

How the Joint Works

The sphere (3) is placed inside the two housings (2). The reinforcing plates (4 & 5) interlock using grooves and holes. A bolt (9) tightens the sphere to the elongated nut (8). The entire setup is clamped together using a nut and a bolt (6). When the nut and the bolt (6) are tightened, the housings press against the sphere and cylindrical detail (1), creating a rigid connection. The shape of the hole (4.1) prevents the hex nut from spinning, so tightening happens just by turning the bolt (6). The tightness of the bolt (6) controls how much the cylindrical detail (1) can move relatively to the sphere (3). A loose bolt allows movement, while a tighter bolt locks the joint in place.

Practical Applications

This joint is rigid and adaptable, making it useful in:

- luminaires (light fixtures): for adjustable lamp arms or mounts;
- human mannequins: allowing adjustable joint movements for positioning.

Key Benefits of This Joint

- secure & stable fixation: the design ensures tight clamping and prevents rotation;
- adjustable motion: the tightening level controls movement flexibility;
- even load distribution: the plastic housings help spread the force evenly, preventing damage;
- versatile materials: it is suitable for metal tubes, wooden rods, and 3D-printed parts.

Summary

This spherical joint securely connects a cylindrical profile (1) to an elongated nut (8) using a sphere, housings, reinforcing plates, and bolts/nuts. It allows adjustable movement or stable fixation based on bolt tightness. The joint is useful in light fixtures and mannequins and is made of metal, wood, and 3D-printed plastic parts.

Figure 5: Spherical joint for cylindrical profiles

2.2.6 Truss Frame Connection

Figure 6 shows a truss structure consisting of two frames (A and C) which are made of rectangular aluminium profiles (20x40x2 mm). These profiles are connected using plates and bolts to form a rigid structure. The plates clamp the profiles on both sides using bolted connections, ensuring a strong and stable assembly.

Types of Connection Plates and Their Functions

- Plate 1 – for right-angle connections. It is used when two profiles are perpendicular (90°) and provides a secure and stable connection.
- Plate 5 – for angles other than 90°. It is used when profiles are not at a right angle and ensures that the truss can accommodate various geometric designs.
- Plate 2 – a variant of plate 1 with a slot (2.1). It is similar to plate 1, but it has an added slot (2.1). These slots allow the connection of one frame to another, forming a larger truss structure. This means that the same plate both connects profiles within a frame and attaches frames together.
- Plates 3 & 4 – for special cases. They are used when plate 2 cannot fulfil both functions (joining profiles and connecting frames). They provide additional support or alternative connections where needed.

Practical Implementation

These truss structures are widely used in the manufacturing of stage podiums. The profiles are made of 20x40x2 mm aluminium rectangular tubes, which are laser-cut and slotted for precision. The connection plates are made of 3mm thick black steel, also laser-cut for accuracy and strength.

Key Benefits of This Truss System

- Rigid construction – the bilateral clamping with bolts ensures a secure and stable connection;
- Modular & expandable – the slot in plate 2 allows easy assembly of multiple frames, making it possible to build large structures;
- Customisable angles – with plate 5, profiles can be connected at angles other than 90°, allowing for more complex designs;

- High-quality materials – the use of aluminium profiles and steel plates ensures durability while keeping the structure lightweight.

Summary

This truss structure is made of two frames (A and C), each built of five aluminium profiles joined by bolted steel plates. Different plates are used depending on whether the profiles meet at 90° angle (Plate 1), an angle different from 90° (Plate 5), or there is a need of additional slots for frame connections (Plate 2). This system is mainly used in stage podium construction, due to its modular, rigid, and customisable design.

Figure 6: Truss frame connection

Key Features of Products Incorporating ARCTONIC:

- Adjustability: the products allow structural modifications without requiring new components;
- Reusability: components can be repeatedly disassembled and reassembled;
- Customisability: design modifications can be easily integrated based on functional needs.

Outcome

The ARCTONIC system has been successfully applied in various industries, including:

- Furniture design: modular shelving, tables, chairs;
- Industrial applications: temporary workstations, scaffolding;
- Automobiles: car roof racks;
- Theatre stage constructions: quick-assembly set designs.

Here are some of the stage sets developed for productions in Ivan Vazov National Theatre in Sofia:

- "The Hague": director - Galin Stoev, scenography - Boris Dalchev (Profile to Sheet Connections used);
- "Antichrist. Chapters VIII, X, XI": director - Stilian Petrov, scenography - Nikola Toromanov (Profile to Sheet Connections used);
- "The Elementary Particles": director - Chris Sharkov, scenography - Nikola Toromanov (Truss Frame Connections used);
- "A Doll's House, Part Two": director - Yassen Peyankov, scenography - Kancho Kasabov (Truss Frame Connections used);
- "Moby Dick": director - Diana Dobрева, scenography - Mira Kalanova (Truss Frame Connections used);
- "The Merchant of Venice": director - Javor Gardev, scenography - Nikola Toromanov (Truss Frame Connections used);
- "Intrigue and Love": director - Asen Shopov, scenography - Asen Shopov (Truss Frame Connections used);
- "Arms and the Man": director - John Malkovich, scenography - Pierre-François Limbosch (Truss Frame Connections used);
- "Baby on Board": director - Vasilena Radeva, scenography - Boris Dalchev (Truss Frame Connections used).

Ivan Vazov National Theatre was awarded with the Ikar 2025 Performing Arts Award by the Union of Bulgarian Actors, for "Masterful technical realisation", for two performances - "The Merchant of Venice" and "Moby Dick". [<https://www.nationaltheatre.bg/en/news/narodniyat-teatr-s-tri-ikar-a-i-nagrada-zavisoki-rezultati-v-oblastta-na-teatralniya-menidzhmnt-i-tvorcheskata-deinost>]

2.3 Products with Polygonal Surface Geometry (PolygonG)

Concept

PolygonG is a method for designing and fabricating welded polygonal sheet metal structures. By implementing digital fabrication, PolygonG enables the creation of lightweight yet rigid structures, suitable for various industries. The digital fabrication techniques used, such as laser cutting and CNC machining, ensure high accuracy in the creation of polygonal elements. Our expertise includes the development of automotive polygonal welded sheet metal components, such as hardtops, bumpers, bull bars, roof racks, and step bars.

Fabrication Process

- **Design Phase**

Parametric CAD modelling determines optimal polygonal geometry. The design process determines how a sheet of metal can be transformed into a 3D shape by deciding which edges will be folded and which will be welded. The goal is to maximise folds and minimise welds, as folds enhance structural integrity and reduce labour-intensive welding.

However, for complex shapes, this balance becomes challenging due to the limitations of the sheet metal bending machines. When a shape is too complex to be fully formed by the machine bending, perforating the fold lines allows for manual bending – similar to origami. This technique simplifies assembly but requires additional welding to reinforce the structure.

In some projects, stress analysis is necessary to assess how a structure performs under specific load. To improve material efficiency, the design process prioritises minimising waste by using optimised cutting patterns.

From a manufacturing perspective, reducing the number of polygons simplifies fabrication. However, in automotive design, factors like aerodynamics and pedestrian safety often require more detailed surface modelling, increasing the polygon count.

A key challenge in automotive applications is blending smooth, flowing shapes (common in modern car design) with a structure made entirely of flat planes. Achieving this balance requires careful attention to both aesthetics and functionality.

- **Material Preparation, Cutting & Folding**

Sheet metal parts are cut with high precision using laser cutting or CNC machining. Once cut, precision folding machines bend the metal according to the design specifications. To streamline the assembly, the cut parts are labelled or marked for easy identification.

- **Assembly & Welding**

Individual sheets are precisely aligned and welded along their edges to form a strong, seamless structure. The welding technique used depends on the type of material (i.e. steel or aluminium) and careful measures should be taken to control distortion and ensure structural integrity.

- **Post-Processing**

The surface is refined through grinding, sanding, and finishing to remove excess welds. Optional treatments like painting, powder coating, or anodising improve durability and enhance aesthetics.

Key Features

- **Structural rigidity:** the welded polygonal framework provides a high strength-to-weight ratio, making it ideal for load-bearing applications;
- **Geometric precision:** digital fabrication techniques ensure precise dimensions, enabling seamless assembly;
- **Customization & scalability:** the modular and adaptable method suits various applications, from furniture and industrial frames to architectural elements. It supports both single-unit fabrication and batch production without requiring additional tooling;
- **Material efficiency:** optimised cutting patterns minimise material waste, making this a sustainable fabrication approach.

Outcome

PolygonG has facilitated the development of durable, high-precision metal structures suitable for a variety of industries. Its integration into automotive design has highlighted both the benefits and challenges of working with polygonal geometries in practical applications.

3 Conclusion

The flexible fabrication-driven design approach provides a powerful methodology for modern product development, particularly within Fab Labs and small-scale manufacturing settings. By implementing digital fabrication technologies, parametric design, and modular assembly techniques, this approach enables high precision, cost efficiency, and adaptability across diverse applications.

While each of the three examined categories – parametric modular structures, ARCTONIC connections, and PolygonG – has unique benefits and challenges, their implementation highlights the potential of flexible manufacturing. Incorporating theoretical insights from computational frameworks (Barrios Hernandez, 2006) and co-creation models (Khan et al., 2023) emphasizes the interdisciplinary nature of this methodology. Future research will explore further optimisations, particularly in the automation of assembly processes and the integration of hybrid material solutions.

This methodology represents a significant step towards a more sustainable and adaptable industrial paradigm, fostering innovation in design and fabrication practices worldwide.

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